

A Study of the Complex Compounds of *N*-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with some Metal Ions. Part XIV. Polarographic Reduction of *N-N'*-Dibenzene sulphonyl *l*-cystine at the Dropping Mercury Electrode

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Polarographic behaviour of *N-N'*-dibenzene sulphonyl *l*-cystine (RSSR) has been investigated at the dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) in the presence of 0.5 *M* NaClO₄ as the supporting electrolyte and 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ % gelatine as the maximum suppressor, at 30°. The effect of variation of *pH* of the solution and that of the concentration of RSSR in buffered solutions have been studied at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$). Diffusion coefficient of RSSR (7.36 × 10⁻⁶ cm²/sec) has been found out in 0.5 *M* NaClO₄ at 30°. The linearity of 'i_d' or of wave height with the concentration of RSSR in well buffered solution of *pH* ≈ 8.50 provides a rapid but precise method for the determination of RSSR down to the amount present in 0.01 mM solution.

Extensive studies have been made on the polarographic behaviour of cysteine¹ and cystine^{2,3}. The present investigation has been carried out with a view to study the effect of the presence of sulphonamido (-SO₂NH-) group on the polarographic behaviour of the same system.

N-N'-Dibenzene sulphonyl *l*-cystine (RSSR) is a disulphide (-S-S-) as well as a disulphonamide,

RSSR has yielded a cathodic wave at the d.m.e. on which the effect of variation of *pH* of the medium and that of RSSR concentration have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-N'-Dibenzene sulphonyl *l*-cystine was prepared by the usual procedure⁴, purified and recrystallised from aqueous-ethanol, m.p. 214°. Found Eqv. wt., 259.60; N, 5.33; Calc. Eqv. wt, 260.00; N, 5.38%. The other reagents were of A.R. quality and their solutions were prepared in air-free conductivity water.

Measurements of *pH* were made with a Cambridge Portable Type *pH*-meter. Polarograms were recorded with a Cambridge Penrecording Polarograph. An external S.C.E. (employing NaCl in place of KCl) viz., Sat. NaCl, Hg₂Cl₂(S)/Hg served as the reference electrode, connected to the cell by means of an agar—0.5 *M* NaClO₄ bridge. The e.m.f. of the

reference electrode was determined precisely with due temperature correction and was found to be -0.2407 volt at 30° . The capillary characteristics were measured in $0.5M$ NaClO_4 solution at -0.50 volt (Vs SCE) at a mercury height of 63.00 cm where $m = 1.572$ mg/sec, $t = 3.571$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.671$ $\text{mg}^{2/3} \text{sec}^{-1/6}$ were found out. $0.5M$ NaClO_4 and $6.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$ bacteriologically pure gelatine were used as the supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. All polarograms were recorded at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$) and at 30° . Necessary corrections were made for residual current in evaluating the diffusion current data and $E_{1/2}$ values. Dissolved air was removed from the solution by bubbling oxygen-free electrolytic hydrogen through the solution for 10 mins. and hydrogen atmosphere was maintained during electrolysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

(a) *Maximum suppressor*: Attempts were made to draw the polarograms of RSSR without a maximum suppressor, when pronounced maxima were obtained. This irregularity was found to be eliminated when gelatine was used as the maximum suppressor. It is true² that different surface active substances acting as maximum suppressors may shift the characteristic $E_{1/2}$ values to more negative potentials. The extent of the shift is dependent on the amount of the maximum suppressor used. Use of same amount of a particular maximum suppressor would affect each polarogram to the same extent.

(b) *Effect of pH on the wave characteristics*: Curves shown in the Fig. 1 are the polarograms of 0.04 mM solutions of RSSR at pH values varying from 1.10 to 11.80 in buffered solutions, all at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$). It is found that at pH 1.10 the reaction

Fig. 1. Polarograms at different pH values. Sensitivity = $1/5$.
70.8 mm. = $1 \mu\text{A}$ (0.04 mM RSSR)

at the d.m.e. started at a potential of -0.06 volt (Vs SCE) but the diffusion current plateau was not well defined (Curve 1, Fig. 1). However, with increase of pH values the reaction started at more and more negative potentials and the diffusion current plateau became more and more defined. But ill-defined wave resulted again at pH values as high as 11.80 (Curve 9, Fig. 1). The irregularities at the beginning of the waves were probably due to the formation of a thin film of Hg SR over the d.m.e. as a result of the reaction² between the reduction

product RSH and Hg. At the later stages when the potential at the d.m.e. became more negative, the intermediate compound Hg SR probably could not be formed or if at all, it would be instantaneously reduced to Hg and RSH and consequently the irregularities that might arise at the early stages of the polarograms were eliminated at the later stages (Fig. 1). Analysis of the waves showed that the characteristic half-wave potential ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$) of RSSR was found to be shifted to more and more negative values with increase of *pH* of the solution (Table 1). For a reversible reaction.

at the d.m.e. the equation of the polarographic wave at 30° is

$$E_{d.m.e.} = (E'_0 - 0.06 \text{ pH}) + 0.03 \log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i^2} \right) \quad \dots (2)$$

where E'_0 is a constant for the system under the experimental conditions. Plotting the applied voltage $E_{d.m.e.}$ (Vs SCE) against $\log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i^2} \right)$ straight lines were obtained through average points, but the slopes were not in conformity with the theoretical value except for the single case at *pH* 8.50, in other cases the slopes deviated from the theoretical value and varied with *pH* (Table 1). The apparent agreement of the slope of the log plot at *pH* 8.50 with the theoretical value is difficult to explain, because such slopes are found to change with the *pH* of the solution, the particular maximum suppressor used and also with the concentration of the maximum suppressor².

TABLE 1

*Slopes of the log plots and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE) values at different *pH* values*

<i>pH</i>	Slope	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE) volt.
1.10	0.064	-0.197
1.98	0.043	-0.235
2.82	0.044	-0.330
4.35	0.048	-0.380
6.10	0.064	-0.450
7.24	0.050	-0.505
8.50	0.030	-0.617
9.20	0.058	-0.630

The variability of the slopes of the log plots at different *pH* values as well as their deviations from the theoretical value indicates the irreversibility of the process occurring at the d.m.e.^{2,5}. The characteristic $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE) values were found to be shifted to more negative values with increase of *pH*. The shift was found to be 54.8 mv on the average per *pH* unit. Similar shift of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values were observed with *L*-cystine². The $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE)

values were plotted against pH , a straight line with a slope of -0.059 was obtained (Curve 1, Fig. 2). The result is approximately in agreement with the theoretical value at 30° .

Fig. 2

(c) *Effect of RSSR concentration on the wave characteristics*: Fig. 3 illustrates the plot of ' i_d ' of the polarograms of solutions containing 0.01 mM to 0.16 mM RSSR per litre at $pH \approx 8.50$ in well buffered medium in presence of $6.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$ gelatine as the maximum suppressor at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$), maintained by adding requisite amount

Fig. 3

of NaClO_4 which served as the supporting electrolyte, against the concentration of RSSR. In calculating the diffusion current data, the polarograph was calibrated by the usual procedure and also the value was extrapolated against wave height by electrolysing a Cd^{2+} solution of known strength under the same condition of supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor and found $1 \mu\text{A} = 354 \text{ m.m.}$ at a sensitivity of one. The ' i_d ' values were calculated from the wave heights of the respective polarograms making due correction for the residual current and diffusion coefficient of RSSR in $0.5M \text{ NaClO}_4$ at $\text{pH } 8.50$ at 30° has also been calculated. Data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Proportionality of diffusion current with RSSR concentration

Concentration of RSSR in mM/lit $\times 10^2$	Wave height m.m.	Corrected ' i_d ' μA	$K_d = \frac{i_d}{C}$	$D = \left[\frac{i_d/607 \text{ n.m.}^{2/3} t^{1/6} C \right]^2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.} \times 10^6$
1	13.00	0.055	5.507	7.369
2	26.00	0.110	5.507	7.369
4	52.00	0.220	5.507	7.369
8	102.30	0.434	5.420	7.140
16	202.60	0.861	5.380	7.030

Average $D = 7.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$, graphically obtained

$D = 7.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$, and for *l*-cystine²

$D = 5.30 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$ in $0.1(N)\text{HCl}$ at 25° .

Constancy of K_d and D within the limits of experimental error clearly indicates the proportionality of diffusion current ' i_d ' with concentration of RSSR and this offers a method for the determination of RSSR polarographically at $\text{pH} \approx 8.50$. The plot of corrected ' i_d ' against the concentration of RSSR was a straight line (Fig. 3). From the slope of this curve the value of K_d was found out to be 5.503 which gave $D = 7.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec.}$ (at 30° in $0.5M \text{ NaClO}_4$) for RSSR.

The polarographic equation (2) becomes

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E'_0 - 0.06 \text{ pH} + 0.03 \log 2 - 0.03 \log i_d \quad \dots (3)$$

when $i = i_d/2$, and at $\text{pH } 8.50$

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = (E'_0 - 0.501) - 0.03 \log i_d \quad \dots (4)$$

or

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E''_0 - 0.03 \log i_d \quad \dots (5)$$

where E''_0 is a constant for the system under experimental condition. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE) values were found to be shifted to more negative values with increase of RSSR concentration and the plot of $\log i_d$ against $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Vs SCE) values was a straight line with a slope of -0.033 (Curve 2, Fig. 2) which was in close agreement with the equation (5). Similar straight lines were also obtained in the case of *l*-cystine².

The observations clearly show that the cathodic wave yielded by RSSR at the d.m.e. is due to its reduction to RSH in an irreversible way involving gain of two electrons. The same type of observation has also been found with the cystine-cysteine system².

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